

Stars and gas in the nearest most metal-poor galaxies I: SBS 0335-052E

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1) REIONIZATION

[Ly α , C IV, O III] emission lines have been detected at $z \sim 7$ in a lensed galaxy at $z \sim 7$ (Stark+15).

This is encouraging for JWST, TMT, e-ELT which will observe the rest-frame UV of thousands of galaxies at $z = 10 - 15$, during the epoch of re-ionization.

Wise+12 predict that it only takes a few pair-instability SNe to reach metallicities of $Z/Z_{\odot} \sim 2\%$ by redshift $z \sim 7$.

Rafelski+14 found that the metallicity of DLAs at $z \sim 5$ is consistent with $Z/Z_{\odot} \sim 2\%$

Because it is unlikely that we will ever be able to observe truly metal-free galaxies, we need to observe the nearest most metal-poor galaxies in order to understand how extreme low metallicity affects the properties of gas and stars.

2) GRAVITATIONAL WAVES

One of the GW events detected by LIGO has been explained by the merging of two BHs of $\geq 20 M_{\odot}$. Such massive stellar BHs are expected to form at low metallicity.

Due to distance, we cannot observe individual metal-poor massive stars likely to yield such BHs.

However, by comparing the integrated light of massive star populations in extremely metal-poor galaxies, with models, we can obtain constraints on the upper IMF of massive star populations.

This is best done in the UV, where massive stars emit most of their radiation.

Nearby galaxy SBS 0335-052E has a metallicity of $Z/Z_{\odot} \sim 4\%$ (Izotov+06).

It is one of the few known galaxies with a metallicity of a few percent which is being studied in detail.

- Famous! Observed from radio (VLA, ALMA) to X-rays (Chandra)
- Blue Compact Dwarf (Izotov+90)
- $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H}) = 7.3$ (Izotov+06)
- $M_* = 5.6 \times 10^6 M_\odot$ (Cormier+2017)
- $\text{SFR} = 0.7 M_\odot/\text{yr}$ (Cormier+2017)
- $[\text{OIII}] 5007 / [\text{OII}] 3727 = 15$ (Izotov+99), i.e., as high as in GP galaxies
- Shows no Ly α emission
- Hosts an Ultra Luminous X-ray source (ULX, Preswitch+13)
- Would be selected as an AGN based on Spitzer color-color diagrams and IRS spectrum (Houck+04)
- Has a companion called SBS 0335-052W

Observations & objectives

For SBS 0335, Wofford & Hayes obtained:

- HST COS G160M + G185M UV spectroscopy ($\sim 1400\text{-}1920 \text{ \AA}$)
- VLT MUSE optical spectroscopy ($\sim 4600\text{-}9400 \text{ \AA}$)

We use our observations to:

1. test our model spectra of stellar populations + gas + dust, which account for stars w/ masses $> 100 M_{\odot}$ (Gutkin+16, Charlot & Bruzual in prep.). Very massive stars are present in the LMC (Crowther+16).
2. test our Bayesian analysis tool which extracts physical properties by comparing observed & model spectra
3. understand the extent to which physical properties are constrained by our models

We are particularly interested in reproducing the He II EL flux because at high- z , it will be the main diagnostic of peculiar massive stars (pop III, very massive stars)

SBS 0335-052E
HST ACS F435W
HST ACS F550M
HST ACS FR656N

650 pc @ 53.6 Mpc

What are plausible sources of ionizing photons in SBS 0335?

1) High Mass X-Ray Binaries? No.

ULX (position error=0.4", Prestwich+13), in vigneted area of COS

2) Accretion onto an IMBH? No.

- Compelling evidence would be the detection of unresolved X-ray emission, spatially coincident with jet/core radio emission.
- No evidence from radio (Johnson+09), X-rays (Thuan+04) of the presence of an IMBH.

4) Stars? Yes.

fig. 11. Part of the spectrum of cluster 3 showing the probable broad Wolf-Rayet emission lines N III λ 4640 and C IV λ 4658 labelled "WR".

3) Shocks from SNRs? Maybe.

- Highest 4686 flux is near clusters which are too old (>6Myr) to emit strongly in the ionizing UV.
- Shocks are an alternative for the high He II flux near these clusters.
- FUSE spectrum shows no evidence of shocks (no O VI 1035 emission, Grimes+09)
- Lack of emission may be due to the extreme low oxygen content.
- Mappings V shock models at extreme low metallicity are under way to know what to expect (Alarie & Moriset in prep.)

Model spectra of stellar populations + gas + dust

- Population synthesis models of **Charlot & Bruzual** in prep.
- Cloudy 13 models (Gutkin+16)
- Metals in gas are depleted to account for their presence in dust grains
- Redden models w/ time-dependent attenuation law of **Charlot & Fall 00**

$$\hat{\tau}_\lambda(t) = \hat{\tau}_\lambda^{\text{BC}} + \hat{\tau}_\lambda^{\text{ISM}} + \Delta\hat{\tau}_\lambda(t)$$

- Input Cloudy parameters:

Z_{ISM}	0.0001, 0.0002, 0.0005, 0.001, 0.002, 0.004, 0.006, 0.008, 0.010, 0.014, 0.017, 0.020, 0.030, 0.040
$\log U_S$	-1.0, -1.5, -2.0, -2.5, -3.0, -3.5, -4.0
ξ_d	0.1, 0.3, 0.5
$\log(n_{\text{H}}/\text{cm}^{-3})$	1, 2, 3, 4
$(\text{C/O})/(\text{C/O})_\odot$	0.10, 0.14, 0.20, 0.27, 0.38, 0.52, 0.72, 1.00, 1.40

- For the star formation history we try the two limiting cases of: constant SF, single stellar population (SSP)
- For the stellar IMF we use Chabrier w/ $M_{\text{up}} = 100, 300 M_\odot$

● VLT MUSE MODELS: — $Z=0.0001$ ☆☆☆ SSP + HIR (Gutkin+16) — Shocks (Allen+08, $Z_{\text{SMC}}=0.004$)
— $Z=0.001$ = = = AGN NLR (Feltre+16)
— $Z_{\odot}=0.014$

● HST COS MODELS: — $Z=0.0001$ ☆☆☆ SSP + HIR (Gutkin+16) — Shocks (Allen+08, $Z_{\text{SMC}}=0.004$)
 — $Z=0.001$ = = = AGN NLR (Feltre+16)
 — $Z_{\odot}=0.014$

$M_{\text{up}}=100 M_{\odot}$

$M_{\text{up}}=300 M_{\odot}$

How did we extract physical properties for SBS 0335?

We use the tool BEAGLE = BayEsian Analysis of GaLaxy sEds (Chevallard+16), which compares observed SEDs w/ models and finds a posterior median of the model parameters.

We fitted the optical and UV observations separately.

Fitting UV+optical simultaneously introduces difficulties due to the different SNRs of the data, line spread functions of the instruments, etc.

By fitting the UV and the optical **independently**, we can obtain independent determinations of the same physical properties.

Can we reproduce simultaneously...

1) the *emission-line fluxes* of the high-ionization lines:

Line ID	Wavelength (Å)	Ion needed	Ionization potential of preceding ion (eV)	Massive star winds	ISM
He II	1640	He ⁺²	54.5	+	+
C IV, C IV	1549, 1551	C ⁺³	47.89	+	+
O III], O III]	1661, 1666	O ⁺²	35.12		+
[CIII], C III]	1907, 1909	C ⁺²	24.38		+

2) and the equivalent widths of the C IV P-Cygni like and nebular em. components?

Yes, with the combination $\{ \text{SSP}, M_{\text{up}} = 300 M_{\odot} \}$:

But O/H is too low. Posterior medians:

Z/Z_{\odot}	$12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$	$\log(\text{C}/\text{O})$
0.0001	6.45	-0.66

Other models fail to reproduce He II 1640:

{ SSP, $M_{\text{up}} = 100 M_{\odot}$ }

Other models fail to reproduce He II 1640:

{ Constant SF, $M_{\text{up}} = 100 M_{\odot}$ }

{ Constant SF, $M_{\text{up}} = 300 M_{\odot}$ }

{SSP, $M_{\text{up}} = 300 M_{\odot}$ } properties w/ and w/o He II removed from the fits:

Optical ages: 2.4, 2.3 Myr

UV ages: 2.3, 3.3 Myr

Adamo+10: 10 Myr

Optical $12+\log(\text{O}/\text{H})$: 7.4, 7.5

Izotov+06: 7.3

UV $\log(\text{C}/\text{O})$: -0.7, -0.45

Garnett+95: = - 0.94

Mass is stars

By fitting the optical continuum of {SSP, $M_{\text{up}} = 300 M_{\odot}$ } we get $M_{*} = 2.9 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$
(Adamo+10 found $1.2 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$).

Summary and conclusions

- Models based on Charlot & Bruzual + Cloudy 13 are able to reproduce observed optical and UV emission line ratios of SBS 0335 in BPT and UV diagnostic diagrams with $M_{\text{up}} = 100$ and $300 M_{\odot}$
- The models and tool presented here are of the kind that will be used to interpret future observations of distant galaxies w/ JWST, TMT, e-ELT.
- He II will be one of our only diagnostics of peculiar massive stars at $z=10-15$
- {SSP, $M_{\text{up}}=300 M_{\odot}$, w/ He II}:
 - only model that reproduces the UV He II 1640, but corresponding O/H is too low
 - fails to reproduce the weaker optical He II 4686
- {SSP, $M_{\text{up}}=300 M_{\odot}$, w/o He II} yields:
 - a slightly higher mass than Adamo+10
 - cluster ages which are much younger
 - a slightly higher O/H
 - a higher C/O relative to Garnett+95
- Tests are under way w/ Cloudy 17.
- We will be observing SBS 0335 with HST/STIS (better spatial resol. in the UV).
- We are observing UV spectra of 8 more extremely metal-poor galaxies w/ COS.

Please come visit!

We are 1.5 hr South of San Diego, CA

View from our campus...

